

Guanidinium Like-Charge Ion Pairing and Oligoarginine Aggregation in Water by NMR, Cryo-Electron Microscopy, and Molecular Dynamics

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Abstract

Like-charge pairing is a physical manifestation of the unique solvation properties of certain ion pairs in water. Water’s high dielectric constant and related charge screening capability significantly influence the interaction between like-charged ions, with the possibility to transform it—in exceptional cases—from repulsion to attraction. Guanidinium cations (Gdm^+) represent a quintessential example of such like-charge pairing due to their specific geometry and electronic structure. In this work, we present experimental validation and quantification of Gdm^+ – Gdm^+ contact ion pairing in water utilizing nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy complemented by molecular dynamics (MD) simulations and density functional theory (DFT) calculations. The observed Gdm^+ – Gdm^+ interaction is attractive albeit weak—about $-0.5 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ —which aligns with theoretical estimation from MD simulations. We contrast the behavior of Gdm^+ with that of NH_4^+ cations, which exhibit no contact ion pairing in water. DFT calculations predict that the NMR chemical shift of Gdm^+ dimers is smaller than that of monomers, in agreement with NMR titration curves that display a nonlinear Langmuir-like behavior. Additionally, we conducted cryo-electron microscopy on oligoarginines R_9 , which, unlike nona-lysines K_9 , exhibit aggregation in water. These results point to like charge pairing of the guanidinium side chain groups, as corroborated also by MD simulations and free energy calculations of aqueous solutions of these peptides.

Introduction

The contact like-charge pairing of ions in water is counterintuitive from the physical point of view since two positively or two negatively charged ions should repel each other according to Coulomb’s law. However, it has been suggested that certain like-charge ions in water attract each other instead.^{1–3} This effect is enabled by the high dielectric constant of the environment (78.5 in water vs. 1 in the gas phase), attenuating the electrostatic repulsion energy at contact between two like-charge ions from $\sim 400 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ in the gas phase to only

several $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ in water. In exceptional cases, this residual repulsion is (over)compensated by attractive van der Waals and other interactions, resulting in net attraction.⁴

Notably, contact like-charge ion-pairing in water has been predicted computationally for planar, quasi-aromatic guanidinium (Gdm^+) cations in numerous MD studies employing both empirical force fields and electronic structure methods.³⁻⁶ Gdm^+ - Gdm^+ pairing may be important in biological contexts since Gdm^+ is the side chain group of the essential amino acid arginine. Close contacts of Gdm^+ moieties are observed in many protein structures,⁶ potentially regulating various protein functions.⁷

On the experimental side, only a few studies currently exist in the literature predicting the Gdm^+ - Gdm^+ pairing in solution, such as X-ray spectroscopy of Gdm^+ ions,⁸ mass spectrometry studies of Gdm^+ water clusters,⁹ and electrophoretic mobility experiments of tetraarginines.¹⁰ Also, the thermodynamic volumetric and activity data of Gdm^+ salts differ significantly from those of salts of simple spherical ions, indicating anomalies in Gdm^+ hydration and Gdm^+ - Gdm^+ interactions.^{11,12} In the biological context, the existence of like-charge Gdm^+ -containing aggregates has been suggested by SAXS and NMR experiments for deca-arginines (R_{10}) in water.¹³ There is also an indirect indication of nona-arginine (R_9) aggregation at phospholipid bilayers, as evidenced by fluorescence assays at supported lipid bilayers.¹⁴

A peek into the molecular origins of the like-charge ion pairs has been provided by computational studies, employing both electronic structure methods^{5,6} and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations with empirical force fields.^{3,5,15} Namely, attraction between Gdm^+ ions is observed when dispersion interactions are included, suggesting that the van der Waals forces—uniquely strong for Gdm^+ due to its very specific quasi-aromatic electronic structure^{4,5,15}—play a key role in the total energy balance. Conspicuously, almost all force fields (FFs) used in classical MD simulations predict Gdm^+ - Gdm^+ like-charge pairing, albeit with different strengths due to favorable van der Waals parameters. In contrast, the interaction between NH_4^+ ions (which serve as a mimic of the lysine side chain), as well as lysine-rich

peptides, leads to mutual repulsion in the above studies employing various levels of theory.

In this work, we focus on two aspects of the $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ like-charge ion pairing by a synergistic combination of two experimental techniques supported by MD simulations. First, we applied NMR titration experiments complemented with force field MD simulations and density functional theory (DFT) calculations of NMR shifts, establishing the experimental free energy of $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ attraction in water for the first time. Second, we expanded the existing experimental data on the interaction of arginine-rich peptides with water, providing conclusive evidence of R_9 aggregation by cryo-electron microscopy (cryo-EM), supported by the classical MD simulations with unbiased free energy.

Methods

Chemicals

Guanidinium chloride, ammonium chloride, sodium chloride, and calcium chloride were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO) with 99 % purity. H-(Lys)₉-OH (K₉), and H-(Arg)₉-OH (R₉) were synthesized by solid-phase peptide synthesis (SPPS) on PS3 peptide synthesizer (Gyros Protein Technologies, USA) using standard Fmoc chemistry protocols, HBTU coupling reagents, and 2-chlorotrityl chloride resin support (0.1 mmol scale and 10 equivalent amino acid excess). Side-chain-protected peptides were cleaved off the resin with a mixture of acetic acid/2,2,2-trifluoroethanol/dichloromethane (1:1:3) for 2 hours at room temperature. The resin was filtered off, reagents and solvents were evaporated to dryness, and residues were treated with the mixture of water/trifluoroacetic acid (TFA)/triisopropylsilane (95:2.5:2:5). The cleaved and deprotected peptides were lyophilized and purified by RP HPLC (Vydac 218TP101522 column) using methanol and water with 0.05 % TFA as solvents. The purity was assessed by analytical RP-HPLC (Vydac 218TP54 column) and LC/MS (Agilent Technologies 6230 ToF LC/MS). The mass was confirmed by MALDI-ToF MS: H-(Lys)₉-OH [M+H]⁺ 1171.9; H-(Arg)₉-OH [M+H]⁺ 1423.9.

NMR Experiments

In order to study specific ion–ion interactions by NMR, we have eliminated the variation in the mean-field electrostatic screening effects by performing our experiments at a constant ionic strength. When experiments are conducted in neat water, the increase of GdmCl concentration changes the ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR shifts of the Gdm⁺ proton and carbon atoms, respectively, as illustrated in Figure S1 in the Supporting Information (SI). Therefore, we prepared a dilution series with decreasing concentrations of GdmCl and NH₄Cl, keeping constant ionic strength by adding NaCl in the appropriate amount. The samples were prepared simultaneously to protect them from solvent evaporation, which could negatively affect the salt concentration. 3.1 M and 3 M solutions of GdmCl and NH₄Cl, as well as 6 M GdmCl were prepared in H₂O/D₂O mixture (volume ratio 9:1) and diluted by 3 M or 6 M NaCl solution, respectively. For both salt concentrations, chemical shifts were referenced to an internal standard *t*-BuOH (1.24 ppm for ^1H and 30.29 ppm for ^{13}C , respectively). The exception to this is the supplementary measurements in neat water, where chemical shifts were referenced to nithomethane as an external standard (4.40 ppm for ^1H and 63.23 ppm for ^{13}C , respectively). The NMR spectra were recorded on a 500 MHz spectrometer (^1H at 500 MHz, ^{13}C at 125.7 MHz) at room temperature (298 K).

Cryo-EM Experiments

Cryo-EM samples of concentrated peptide solutions were prepared on either 300 mesh 2/2 Quantifoil or C-flat EM grids (Electron Microscopy Sciences, USA), on which 10 nm protein A-conjugated colloidal gold particles (Au-NP) were preadsorbed (Aurion, Netherlands). Au-NP adsorbed grids were then glow-discharged (30 s, 40 mA) in a Quorum GLOQUBE Plus system. An aliquot (3.0 μL) of either i) 100 mM solution of nona-arginine (R₉) or nona-lysine (K₉) in 150 mM NaCl with added 100 mM CaCl₂ prior to sample freezing or ii) 150 mM NaCl with added 100 mM CaCl₂ prior to sample freezing was applied to the carbon side of EM grids, and subsequently blotted for 2.0 s at blot force -7 and plunge-frozen into

the precooled liquid ethane with a Vitrobot Mark IV (FEI, USA).

Cryo-electron micrographs of vitrified samples were collected using a transmission electron microscope JEOL JEM-2100PLUS (JEOL, Japan) equipped with a TemCam-XF416(ES) (TVIPS, Germany) camera, using an Elsa cryo-transfer holder model 698 (Gatan), at accelerating voltage of 200 keV. Grid mapping and image acquisition were performed using SerialEM software¹⁶ at a nominal magnification of $80\times$ and $2,500\times$, respectively. High-magnification images were recorded at $60,000\times$ nominal magnification (0.194 nm pixel size) with a $-10\mu\text{m}$ defocus value. To minimize radiation damage during image acquisition, the low-dose mode in SerialEM software was used, and the electron dose was kept below $100\text{ e}^-/\text{\AA}^2$.

Each high-magnification image of the vitrified samples was first converted to an 8-bit format and binned by 4 to enhance feature recognition. Subsequently, a 250-pixel size square region was selected from each image, the corresponding Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) was calculated using the respective command in Fiji software,¹⁷ and the normalized radial profile of the FFT power spectra was then measured using Radial Profile Angle plugin of Fiji. In addition, each selected image region was binarized using the center of the gray-level histogram as the threshold, and the resulting spatial autocorrelation function was calculated using a MATLAB script.

Electronic Structure Calculations

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations for the carbon-NMR chemical shifts were performed using the single point Gauge-Independent Atomic Orbital (GIAO) method with the B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ basis set at the B3LYP-D3/cc-pVDZ optimized geometry (denoted as B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ//B3LYP-D3/cc-pVDZ). The calculations were carried out on a $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ dimer hydrated with 12 water molecules and compared to a Gdm^+ monomer hydrated with 6 water molecules. Additionally, the levels of theory B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ//B3LYP-D3/aug-cc-pVDZ and B3LYP/6-311++G(2d,p)//B3LYP-D3/6-311+G(d,p) were tested for the same system, see Table S1 for a full summary. NH_4^+ dimers—prepared

as hydrated monomers with 4 water molecules per each and calculated at the same level of theory—were found unstable and dissociated, resulting in a formation of solvent-separated ion-pair instead, Figure S3. Calculated carbon-NMR shifts were subtracted from the reference carbon-NMR shift tetra-methyl silane (TMS) at the same level of theory. Additionally, carbon-NMR shift calculations were performed with the polarizable continuum model (PCM) at B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ//B3LYP-D3/aug-cc-pVDZ level of theory for $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ dimers.^{18,19} The carbon-NMR shifts were also calculated for the $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ dimers with the central carbon distance from 2.9 Å to 5.5 Å in order to determine the cut-off distance beyond which the carbon-NMR shift remains relatively constant, Figure S4. The Grimme empirical dispersion correction was used for geometry optimizations of microhydrated clusters at the B3LYP level of theory.²⁰ All DFT calculations are performed with the Gaussian16 suite of codes.²¹

Molecular Dynamics Simulations

All-atom MD simulations were designed to resemble the composition of aqueous solutions used in the NMR and cryo-EM experiments and provide direct atomistic insights into the studied phenomena.

To resemble NMR systems, 400 GdmCl and 330 NH_4Cl ion pairs were dissolved in 5,550 water molecules to achieve the desired concentration of ~ 3 M. Systems with lower GdmCl and NH_4Cl concentrations were prepared by adjusting the amount of Gdm^+ to [10, 25, 50, 100, 200] or NH_4^+ to [10, 20, 40, 80, 160] and adding the corresponding amount of sodium cations to have a total of 400 and 330 ion pairs, respectively. Similarly, 1100 GdmCl ion pairs were dissolved in 5,500 water molecules to achieve ~ 6.0 M concentration, and [50, 100, 200, 400, 800] Gdm^+ with added sodium were used to create lower concentrations. Thus, the total ionic strength of the solutions was always kept constant as in the experiments. Three different FFs were tested for GdmCl : Kirkwood-Buff (KB) FF,^{22,23} which does not predict $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ pairing; the updated version of KB model (KB2) that introduces Gdm^+-

Gdm⁺ pairing into the original model,²⁴ and prosECCo75 model²⁵—the CHARMM36²⁶ derivative that incorporates the electronic polarization via charge scaling²⁷ and also suggests Gdm⁺–Gdm⁺ pairing. For NH₄Cl simulations, only the prosECCo75 model was used. The simulations were 500 ns long, with the first 100 ns omitted from all analyses.

For comparison with the cryo-EM data, both biased and unbiased MD simulations were conducted for aqueous solutions of R₉ and K₉ peptides. First, free energy MD simulations were performed using the accelerated weight histogram (AWH) method with multiwalker sampling.²⁸ In each simulation, only two peptides (either R₉ or K₉) were present. Two ionic conditions were examined: one with 18 chloride counterions and another with 104 CaCl₂ and 156 NaCl ion pairs, corresponding to ionic concentrations of 100 mM and 150 mM, respectively. The latter condition resembles the ionic environment used in the cryo-EM experiments. Each simulation system comprised 55,654 water molecules for the R₉ systems and 55,669 water molecules for the K₉ systems. The reaction coordinate for the free energy calculations was defined as the center-of-mass distance between the two peptides, sampled over a range from 0.2 to 5.5 nm. Free energy profiles were generated using eight walkers, each initialized from configurations with peptide–peptide distances of 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3, 4, and 5 nm, respectively. These initial configurations were extracted from a preliminary AWH simulation performed on systems containing additional ions and conducted with a single walker. For AWH simulations involving only counterions, the extra ions were removed from the initial configurations. All free energy profiles were corrected for volume entropy effects²⁹ ($+2k_{\text{B}}T \ln(r)$) and subsequently shifted to zero at the largest distances, where peptide interactions are negligible. For all AWH calculations, the target distribution was set to be uniform. The initial diffusion constant was set to $5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ nm}^2 \cdot \text{ps}$, and the initial error estimate was $10 \text{ kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$. The umbrella potential was applied with a force constant of $100,000 \text{ kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{nm}^{-2}$.

Two independent AWH runs were carried out for each system. In the first set of runs, we used a looser (“covering”) criterion for exiting the initial (exploration) phase before

entering the final stage, see Ref. 28 and the GROMACS manual for details. In this case, a single “covering” of the reaction coordinate is reached as soon as the reaction coordinate is *collectively* traversed by all walkers. This behavior is achieved by setting the so-called “cover diameter” to zero. The growth factor γ for the exponential phase was equal to 3 in these simulations. In the second set, a stricter criterion was enforced, which required that at least one walker sampled the entire reaction coordinate independently. In these runs, the cover diameter was set to 5.3 nm (*i.e.*, the full length of the sampling interval), and the growth factor was set to 2. As a result, the initial exploration phase finished relatively quickly with the looser criterion (~ 0.5 – 1.5 μs of collective simulated time), whereas it took significantly longer with the stricter criterion (~ 4 μs for the K_9 systems, ~ 8 μs for the R_9 system with excess ions, and was not achieved for the R_9 system with only counterions). The total AWH simulation time was: (i) for all K_9 -containing simulations and the R_9 simulations using the looser criterion, 625 ns per walker (an aggregate simulation time of 5 μs per energy profile, 8 walkers \times 625 ns); (ii) for the R_9 system with excess ions and the stricter criterion, 1.5 μs per walker (total 12 μs); (iii) for the R_9 system with only counterions and the stricter criterion, 2 μs per walker (total 16 μs). The reported free energy profiles are the averages obtained from the two runs, shown together with their corresponding standard deviations. Additional technical details of the AWH method are available in the original publication.²⁸

Next, we employed unbiased MD simulations to investigate how peptide concentration influences peptide interactions in aqueous solutions. Specifically, simulations were performed at two different peptide concentrations and under various ionic strengths. 6 and 16 peptide molecules (R_9 or K_9), corresponding to concentrations of approximately 20 mM and 50 mM, were solvated in aqueous solutions containing either no salt (apart from chloride counterions necessary to neutralize the positive net charge of the peptides), 130 mM NaCl, or 130 mM CaCl₂. All simulation systems contained 15,856 water molecules. The proECCo75 FF was employed for these simulations. These simulations were 2 μs long, with the first 500 ns omitted from the analysis.

All MD simulations were performed using a leap-frog integrator with a time step of 2 fs in GROMACS engine.³⁰ We adopted simulation protocols in accord with previously used and recommended for the corresponding FFs. Buffered Verlet lists³¹ were used to keep track of atomic neighbors. The input cutoff for short-range electrostatic interactions was set to 1.2 nm (prosECCo75) or 1 nm (KB and KB2). Long-range electrostatics was treated using smooth particle mesh Ewald (PME) algorithm.³² The cutoff for Lennard–Jones interactions was set to 1.2 nm with the forces switched to zero starting at a distance of 1.0 nm³³ (prosECCo75) or simply set to 1.0 nm (KB and KB2). The temperatures of 300 K (for the GdmCl and NH₄Cl solutions) and 310 K (for R₉ and K₉ solutions) were maintained by the Nosé–Hoover thermostat^{34,35} with a coupling time constant of 1 ps (prosECCo75) or v-rescale thermostat³⁶ with a coupling time of 0.1 ps (KB and KB2). The Parrinello–Rahman barostat³⁷ with a coupling time constant of 5 ps (prosECCo75) or 2 ps (KB and KB2) and compressibility of $4.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ bar}^{-1}$ was maintaining the pressure of 1 bar. Water was simulated as a CHARMM-specific TIP3P model^{38,39} (prosECCo75) or SPC/E model⁴⁰ (KB and KB2). Bonds in solute molecules involving hydrogen atoms were constrained using P-LINCS,^{41,42} whereas the geometry of water was constrained using SETTLE.⁴³ In the case of KB simulations, all other covalent bonds were also constrained, following the original simulation protocol.²³

Results and Discussion

Like-Charge Pairing of Gdm⁺ Ions in Water

Figure 1A shows the experimental NMR chemical shifts with increasing Gdm⁺ or NH₄⁺ concentrations in GdmCl and NH₄Cl solutions, respectively. The experiments were performed at a constant ionic strength (*i.e.*, at constant mean-field electrostatic screening of studied solutions) of approximately 3 M, which was necessary for accurate free energy determination of ion-specific Gdm⁺–Gdm⁺ pairing.⁴⁴ The approach of Gdm⁺/Na⁺ titration has previously

been demonstrated to be successful in measuring the electrophoretic mobility of GdmCl solutions.¹⁰

Figure 1: A) The concentration dependence of ¹H NMR chemical shift on the Gdm⁺ or NH₄⁺ concentration in an aqueous solution, where a constant ionic strength of ~3 M is maintained by adding NaCl. B) The like-charge pairing of the Gdm⁺ cations as a function of Gdm⁺ concentration in an aqueous solution, where a constant ionic strength of ~3 M is maintained by adding NaCl. Data for the three MD force fields are compared: prosECCo75 and KB2 models show nonlinear behavior and, at the same time, capture contact ion Gdm⁺-Gdm⁺ pairing, while KB model shows the linear behavior and does not capture contact ion Gdm⁺-Gdm⁺ pairing. The blue inset rectangle exemplifies Gdm⁺-Gdm⁺ contact ion pairing from MD simulations using the prosECCo75 force field.

The nonlinear change in the observed ^1H NMR chemical shift indicates cation–cation binding, as shown for GdmCl solutions. It cannot be attributed to, *e.g.*, $\text{Gdm}^+\text{-Cl}^-$ pairing, which is essentially linearly dependent on concentration, as calculated from the corresponding MD simulations radial distribution functions (RDFs) (Figure S5 in the SI), showing nearly identical profiles across all tested concentrations. The measured difference $\Delta\delta$ in ^1H NMR shift can be used to characterize and quantify the energetics of binding by calculating the dissociation constant K_d .⁴⁵ The dependence of $\Delta\delta$ on Gdm^+ concentration follows a typical Langmuir isotherm, which can be fitted as:

$$\Delta\delta = \delta - \delta_0 = c \cdot A + \frac{\Delta\delta_{max} \cdot c}{K_d + c}, \quad (1)$$

where A is a linear constant with units of chemical shift per molar concentration and $\Delta\delta_{max}$ is the maximum change in chemical shift observed for the nonlinear portion of the curve at saturation.

We calculated the dissociation constant K_d for 3 M GdmCl solution to be ~ 0.8 . This value can be converted to the free energy of binding using the formula $\Delta G_b = -kT \ln K_b$, where K_b is the binding constant, which is the inverse of the dissociation constant K_d . Using this approach, we calculated the binding free energy of Gdm^+ ions to be approximately -0.2 kT or -0.5 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ at room temperature. Thus, Gdm^+ ions form a weakly stabilized contact ion pair in a solution of a 3 M ionic strength. This finding provides the first experimental quantification of $\text{Gdm}^+\text{-Gdm}^+$ contact ion pairing strength in aqueous solutions. In the solution of 6 M ionic strength, the like-charge pairing is stronger, which is expected since the higher ionic strength further attenuates the like charge electrostatic repulsion. This behavior is illustrated in Figure S2, where a non-linear increase in ^1H NMR shift leads to a ΔG_b of -1.2 kT or -3.0 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$.

Finally, as a negative control, we examined the NH_4Cl system where MD simulations predict no like-charge pairing.^{5,6} The measured ^1H NMR chemical shifts for the NH_4Cl solution at a constant ionic strength of 3 M exhibit no discernible trend, Figure 1A. This

behavior is qualitatively different from the GdmCl experiments, indicating the absence of attraction for NH_4^+ ions in water.

Since the experimental NMR measurements cannot provide all the molecular details of the like-charge ion pairing, we performed MD simulations of the investigated systems. We modeled systems with varying concentrations of GdmCl and NH_4Cl , maintaining constant ionic strengths of approximately 3 M or 6 M by adding the appropriate amount of NaCl (see Methods for details). For the simulations involving Gdm^+ , we utilized three different FFs: KB, KB2, and prosECCo75. For systems containing NH_4^+ , we used the prosECCo75 FF only. Ion pairing was quantified using two different distance cutoffs. The first cutoff was set at 3.9 Å for $\text{C}_z\text{-C}_z$ and 4.9 Å for $\text{N}_z\text{-N}_z$ in GdmCl and NH_4Cl , respectively. These values represent the maxima in the corresponding RDFs, Figure S6. The second cutoff of 4.5 Å was applied to both systems and derived from NMR chemical shift PCM/GIAO calculations on the $\text{Gdm}^+\text{-Gdm}^+$ dimer (see Methods). The calculated ^{13}C NMR shift does not significantly change beyond a distance of 4.5 Å between guanidinium carbons, see Figure S4. Therefore, we presume that beyond this cutoff, the Gdm^+ cations do not “feel” each other in the NMR experiments. This observation can also be extended to the interpretation of ^1H NMR experiments.⁴⁶

Our MD data, summarized in Figure 1B, show the calculated contact probability as a function of Gdm^+ concentration in GdmCl solutions at a constant ionic strength of ~ 3 M. Notably, two of the three FFs examined—KB2 and prosECCo75—exhibit a nonlinear trend that aligns with the NMR experiments. This trend indicates significant binding between Gdm^+ cations, with prosECCo75 showing slightly stronger attractive interactions. Importantly, only these two FFs capture the contact ion pairing of Gdm^+ cations, as shown in the inset of Figure 1B and the representative RDFs in Figure S6. In contrast, the KB model exhibits a linear trend, which indicates a lack of binding between Gdm^+ cations for this force field. Similarly, the data for NH_4Cl solutions reveal an exclusively linear trend with increasing NH_4^+ concentration, Figure S8. All these conclusions hold true across both

concentrations and cutoffs used to distinguish contact ion pairing, Figures S8 and S9.

The RDFs shown in Figure S6 can also be converted into the potential of mean force, which provides a rough estimate of the binding free energy ΔG_b between a pair of Gdm⁺ ions, Figure S7. Using RDFs derived from MD simulations of ~ 3 M GdmCl solution, the estimated ΔG_b from the energy minima is found to be -1.1 and -0.6 kJ \cdot mol⁻¹ for the prosECCo75 and KB2 models, respectively, Table S2, which is in accord with our experimental NMR data.

We also compared the experimental NMR results with DFT calculations of GIAO NMR chemical shifts for optimized microhydrated Gdm⁺ clusters, Figure S3. Specifically, we calculated the ¹³C NMR chemical shift for a Gdm⁺-Gdm⁺ dimer hydrated with 12 water molecules and compared it to that of a Gdm⁺ monomer hydrated with 6 water molecules at various levels of theory. In all cases, the ¹³C NMR shift of the dimer was consistently lower than that of the monomer, with differences ranging from 0.8 to 1.4 ppm, Table S1. The computational prediction that the ¹³C NMR chemical shift is lower in the dimer compared to the monomer is also experimentally validated. In addition, ¹³C NMR experiments for GdmCl in 6 M ionic strength solutions demonstrate a nonlinear behavior of the chemical shift with increasing GdmCl concentration, similar to the ¹H NMR experiments, as shown in Figure S2. The estimated ΔG_b from the experimental ¹³C NMR data is -3.7 kJ \cdot mol⁻¹, which is consistent with the experimental ¹H NMR data.

Like-Charge Pairing of Oligoarginines in Water

To further experimentally address guanidinium-based ion pairing, we investigated the aggregation of biologically relevant oligopeptides in water using cryo-EM, comparing the behavior of Gdm⁺-containing peptides (nona-arginine, R₉) with NH₄⁺-based ones (nona-lysine, K₉). The rationale behind this choice is that R₉ peptides are widely used as cell-penetrating peptides, with their aggregation properties in bulk being relevant for their translocation efficiency.^{14,47}

Cryo-EM is often utilized to resolve protein structures or to image self-assembling sys-

tems such as lipid membranes and organic or metallic nanoparticles. Nevertheless, it can also visualize solutions of nanoscopic molecules,⁴⁸ as demonstrated with heavy atom nanocrystals⁴⁹ and surfactant micelles.⁵⁰ Images of unstructured systems, such as peptides in solution, often exhibit low contrast due to the small size and composition differences compared to the surrounding bulk amorphous ice,^{50,51} which limits the obtainable information. Here, to enhance the contrast and thus effectively assess differences in aggregation of different peptides, we modulated the microscope Contrast Transfer Function (CTF) by shifting the image defocus to large values ($-10\ \mu\text{m}$). By acquiring images at high defocus values, the signal from low spatial frequencies (*i.e.*, lower resolution information) is increased, thus enhancing the contrast.^{52,53} This approach allows us to visualize features that would otherwise be difficult to identify. However, it should be noted that high-frequency/high resolution information is significantly reduced with this method.

To maintain proper vitrification of the samples into glassy ice, the peptide concentration was maintained at 100 mM, but aggregation and clustering were enhanced by increasing the ionic strength of the buffer via the addition of 100 mM CaCl_2 . The cryo-EM images of the two peptide solutions show distinctly different patterns and features, visible in both grayscale and binarized images, see Figure 2. The R_9 peptide solution displays characteristic spatial clustering of the signal, while the K_9 peptide solution possesses negligible features or clusters. The spatial clustering of similar gray-value pixels in the former system is consistent with previously reported images of surfactant micelles,⁵⁰ suggesting the presence of nanometric objects in the solution.

The two-dimensional FFT power spectra of the respective images further underscore the differences between the two peptide solutions. The R_9 solution displays a strong low-frequency signal and a first Thon ring,⁵⁴ characteristic of significant contrasted features within the images. Conversely, the K_9 solution shows a lower intensity in the low spatial frequency region, indicative of fewer features. Comparing these images with those obtained from buffer-only samples (150 mM NaCl and 100 mM CaCl_2) reveals that the signal from

Figure 2: Representative cryo-EM images of 100 mM R₉ (top, blue) and K₉ (bottom, red) in 150 mM NaCl and 100 mM CaCl₂ buffer, along with their corresponding binarized images used for autocorrelation function calculations. The images display distinct differences in the spatial distribution of the intensity signals. The R₉ peptide solution exhibits clusters of pixels with the same gray values, while the K₉ peptide solution has a more diffuse distribution. Calculation of the median FFT from all replicates ($n = 205$ for R₉ and $n = 152$ for K₉) confirms significant differences between the two peptides. The scale bar for the cryo-EM images is 50 nm.

the K₉ peptide solution is close to that of a peptide-free solution, Figure S10A.

The analysis of the radial profile of the respective FFT power spectra confirms that R₉ displays an enhanced signal in the 0.09–0.2 nm⁻¹ spatial frequency region, with an additional peak located at 0.4 nm⁻¹ (Figure 3A). In contrast, the FFT of K₉ images show only a minor increase in signal at 0.15 nm⁻¹ without any additional Thon rings present. When compared to the FFT of buffer-only images, it is evident that the K₉ power spectra mostly overlap with peptide-free samples, Figure S10C, suggesting the absence of significant features in these images. Conversely, the distinct first and second peaks in the R₉, which are absent in buffer-only solutions (Figure S10B), indicate that the observed spatial clustering is a unique characteristic of the R₉ images.

Figure 3: (A) Radial profiles derived from FFT power spectra images that show a significantly different spatial signal distribution for R₉ (blue) compared to K₉ (red). (B) Spatial autocorrelation function curves calculated from cryo-EM images, representing the correlation of grayscale values as a function of pixel distance from each pixel. For R₉ (blue), the data reveal strong positive correlation (same gray values) at short pixel distances, followed by pronounced anticorrelation (opposite gray values), and ultimately a stochastic distribution at longer distances (tail baseline), altogether suggesting the presence of clusters. In contrast, the K₉ (red) data show a rapid decay to stochastic values, indicating minimal spatial correlation. Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation, based on $n = 205$ frames for R₉ and $n = 152$ frames for K₉.

Analyzing the spatial autocorrelation function (ACF) of the images further supports the above findings, Figure 3B. The gray-value correlations for K₉ rapidly decay to no correlation after three neighboring pixels, with minimal anticorrelation (*i.e.*, negative ACF values). In contrast, R₉ signal remains correlated for approximately five pixels and subsequently exhibits strong anticorrelation (opposite gray values). Comparing the ACF curves of the peptides solutions with those of the buffer-only images further confirms that K₉ more closely resembles a peptide-free scenario, Figure S10D and S10E. While our analysis does not enable precise determination of cluster sizes due to resolution loss caused by high defocus during acquisition, it nevertheless demonstrates that the presence of peptides with guanidinium moieties significantly promotes aggregation/clustering compared to those with ammonium groups.

To further corroborate the cryo-EM findings, we conducted MD simulations of R₉ and K₉ peptides in aqueous solutions. First, we estimated the peptide-peptide interaction free energy using AWH simulations with only two peptides present in the system. As shown in Figure 4A, the free energy profiles reveal that only R₉ peptides exhibit a negative (*i.e.*, favorable) binding free energy, and this is observed only when a sufficient concentration of ions is present, which actually represents our cryo-EM conditions. This indicates that R₉ peptides can have a stable binding configuration under conditions that more closely resemble biological environments, where there are sufficient ions and charged molecules present. When only counterions are available, R₉ peptides display some energy minima along the free energy curve; however, these minima correspond to overall unfavorable interactions. In contrast, K₉ peptides do not form any favorable binding configurations under any of the conditions examined. We also calculated the average number of side-chain contacts between the two peptides in these AWH simulations. Specifically, we counted the number of C_z-C_z or N_z-N_z interactions within a 6 Å cutoff. Our results show that the energy minimum for R₉-R₉ interactions arises from multiple contacts between guanidinium side-chain groups, which is not the case of K₉ peptides.

Figure 4: (A) Free energy profiles as a function of the center-of-mass distance between two R₉ or K₉ peptides obtained from AWH simulations (left). The average number of side-chain contacts between the peptides, as sampled during these simulations, is also shown along with the corresponding standard deviation (right). Two ionic conditions were tested: aqueous solutions containing only chloride counterions and aqueous solutions with 150 mM NaCl and 100 mM CaCl₂. (B) Radial distribution functions for C_z-C_z (in Gdm⁺ groups, top) and N_z-N_z (in NH₄⁺ groups, bottom) calculated from unbiased MD simulations of R₉ or K₉ in various aqueous solutions. Note that intramolecular interactions within a single peptide are excluded from these RDFs.

Then, we performed unbiased MD simulations at two different peptide concentrations (20 mM and 50 mM) in aqueous solutions containing either counterions only or NaCl/CaCl₂ at a concentration of 130 mM. The aggregation behavior of R₉ and K₉ peptides was analyzed using RDFs for the C_z-C_z (Gdm⁺) and N_z-N_z (NH₄⁺) atom pairs, respectively. As shown in Figure 4B, the RDFs (excluding intramolecular contacts of C_z-C_z and N_z-N_z) display distinctly different patterns. The $g_{C_z-C_z}(r)$ functions exhibit sharp first peaks at a distance of approximately 0.39 nm across all studied systems, indicating significant interactions between Gdm⁺ groups of arginine residues in different R₉ molecules. In contrast, the $g_{N_z-N_z}(r)$ functions do not show any distinct peaks, suggesting a lack of attractive interactions between ammonium groups in different K₉ peptides. Notably, the interactions between Gdm⁺ groups is enhanced by either increasing ionic strength or peptide concentration, similar to our observations in AWH simulations.

Conclusions

In this work, we performed NMR titration experiments on aqueous solutions of GdmCl and NH₄Cl, maintaining constant ionic strength by adding appropriate amounts of NaCl. For the first time, we experimentally quantified the strength of Gdm⁺-Gdm⁺ like-charge ion pairing; an effect that was not observed for NH₄⁺ ions. In particular, the pairing strength is approximately -0.5 kJ·mol⁻¹ in a solution with an ionic strength of 3 M. Our experimental findings are in excellent agreement with theoretical predictions from MD simulations and are further corroborated by results from DFT calculations. Next, we performed cryo-EM experiments on nona-arginines and nona-lysines in aqueous solutions containing NaCl and CaCl₂. We conclusively demonstrated that R₉, unlike K₉, aggregate in water. This finding was further corroborated by unbiased and free energy MD simulations of solvated peptides, where R₉ (but not K₉) exhibited a tendency to interact, especially under ionic conditions that more closely resemble biological environments. Overall, our combined use of NMR and

cryo-EM techniques, alongside theoretical methods, reveals that Gdm⁺-containing species exhibit counterintuitive like-charge ion pairing. This finding underscores the distinctive physicochemical behavior of Gdm⁺ ions, which is driven by their specific chemical properties, unique electronic structure, and water solvation.

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TOC Graphic

